

AGENT BASED SIMULATION AND GIS MAPPING OF TUBERCULOSIS TRANSMISSION: A CASE STUDY IN DAET, CAMARINES NORTE

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis or TB is still a major health concern, more so in developing countries, apart from Philippines where there are about 591, 000 new cases of the disease every year. This research aims to describe transmission of TB in Daet, Camarines Norte using GIS and ABS in spatial and temporal modelling of the disease to determine hotspots that will benefit from targeted interventions. Based on the eight barangays described in the study and with the use of NetLogo simulation models and QGIS mapping, focus interviews were conducted with healthcare professionals and selected community members. This talking points Alawihao and Bibirao barangays as districts that are always affected with factors such as mobility rates or coverage of interventions known to alter transmission rates. Using GIS mapping, distance from the health facilities was also confirmed important in preventing the spread of the diseases. The outcomes demonstrate how could be used further ABS and GIS in order to enhance the understanding of the public health processes with the view to refining the directions of the TB topic, in the further assessment of the real time impact of a disease and in the making of models of potential future outbreaks. Enhancing the recovery rate, and reducing emphasis on a given health program to check on transmission is another mechanism.

Keywords: *Tuberculosis, Geographic Information Systems, Agent-Based Simulation, Health*

I. INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is an airborne infectious disease caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, which primarily affects the lungs but can involve any part of the body. It is still one of the primary leading causes of illness and mortality throughout the world particularly in low and middle-income countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), TB is estimated to contribute approximately 1.5 million deaths per year making it among the leading public health concerns [15]. The Philippines is included in the list of countries with a huge TB burden providing 11% of the worldwide TB incidence each year with an estimation of 591,000 new cases yearly [9]. This study recommends the application of Geographic Information System (GIS) and Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) for the assessment of TB transmission and for the subsequent identification of appropriate mass intervention strategies needed in Daet, Camarines Norte community.

RELATED LITERATURE

Kasaie et al. [6] identified that Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) plays an important role in disease spreading modeling as compared to more traditional approaches of studying diseases including epidemiological ones that are based solely on individuals' aggregate data and do not take into account individual and social interactions. Unlike these traditional models, ABS combines the bottom up structure where it

models the direct actions of the agents involved in a system without having to add further parameters for characteristics such as age or socio-economic status. This method helps to get a better view of how diseases spread and, therefore, leads to better response from public health services.

According to Hernandez et al. [2] one of the key advantages of using Agent Based Simulation (ABS) for instance, is that it focuses on micro data instead of macro data. It looks for new patterns that emerge how individuals behave. This makes it easier for the researcher to get a better conceptual understanding of the transmission processes of diseases compared to traditional models. Furthermore, ABS may contain other characteristics influencing the health-related behaviors and outcomes like income, mobility, and healthcare access.

Hunter et al. [3] used agent-based simulation (ABS) to model infectious disease studies, highlighting the flexibility in their development due to a lack of standard protocols. It identifies commonalities and differences across existing models, using these insights to develop a taxonomy of agent-based epidemiological simulations and demonstrate its application. Hence, one of the examples of study that utilized agent-based simulation (ABS) in Tuberculosis was the study of Udall and Searle [14] in which it applied ABS to model TB spread in South Africa's informal settlements, highlighting high population density and low treatment rates as key factors. It supports data-driven policymaking to reduce TB cases and deaths.

Furthermore, Khaliq et al. [7] explores the link between TB incidence and climatic factors in Pakistan from 2007 to 2020. It finds a rising trend in TB cases, with high-risk areas correlating to higher temperatures in populous provinces. Machine learning models predict disease risk, with SVM providing the most accurate results. This approach offers valuable insights for targeted TB control efforts.

Moreover, Kasaie, Dowdy, and Kelton [5] also used agent-based simulation (ABS) to model TB transmission in high-incidence settings, focusing on individual-level dynamics and hierarchical contact networks. It evaluates secondary infection timing and network effects, with sensitivity analysis confirming result reliability. While Kasaie, Andrews, Kelton, and Dowdy [4] models the impact of household contact tracing on TB incidence, showing reductions of 10-15% and up to 27% with preventive therapy. Most household transmission occurs before diagnosis, limiting its standalone effectiveness. Enhanced

coverage and integration into broader strategies are essential.

Moreover, in public health research Shaweno et al. [13] confirmed that Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are useful when it comes to disease mapping. GIS makes it possible for researchers to view where diseases are prevalent so that they can identify locations that require intervention. Demographics such as population density or proximity to medical facilities are important to consider since they can influence the rate of disease spread.

Meyer-Rath et al. [8] provide an example of this by performing GIS mapping of tuberculosis in South Africa and illustrating how such an approach can lead to appropriate public health interventions. Aranha et. al. [1] also used GIS to analyze the patterns of tuberculosis in wild boar and red deer from 2006 to 2016, after the legislation on "Epidemiologic Risk Areas for Bovine Tuberculosis in Large Game." GIS allowed the spatial-temporal distribution analysis of 9844 animals over 11 hunting seasons, and higher occurrences of tuberculosis were found in wild boar and high-risk southern areas. This research underlines the role of GIS in the impact assessment of legislation, informing targeted interventions and optimizing mitigation strategies for wildlife tuberculosis.

Furthermore, Rasam, Shariff, and Dony [10] showed a combination of GIS and geostatistics mapping 102 high TB-risk locations in Shah Alam and determining key factors, like socioeconomic status, housing, mobility, and urbanization. This showed how it is possible to predict TB risks with the use of GIS, and to further target interventions. While Rasam et al. [11] study applied GIS-based multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) model to rank TB risk zones, validating results with 2015 data.

Moreover, Rosli, Shah, and Mahmood [12] systematic review explore GIS's role in identifying TB clusters, focusing on spatial scan statistics for outbreak detection and surveillance. It highlights GIS's effectiveness in TB control and prevention but notes limitations in using aggregated data and spatial boundaries. GIS is particularly useful for real-time surveillance and decision-making in developing countries.

Combining a computational model, Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) enables effective analysis of tuberculosis transmission patterns. This approach emulates interactions between individuals and graphs the distribution of diseases to identify specific areas for intervention.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Type of Research

This research employs both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection and analysis in order to achieve the desired results. The quantitative aspect involves the application of Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in order to create and display the spread of TB in 8 Barangays (Calasgasan, Camambugan, Alawihao, Dogongan, Bibirao, Pamorangan, Magang, Mancruz) of Daet, Camarines Norte. This enables the quantitative modeling of the disease transmission pattern to obtain information on the rates of infections, areas of high transmission and effects of various control measures. This approach makes use of the concepts of ABS and GIS to show how the disease transmission occurs spatially and temporally within the community.

On the other hand the qualitative research aspect of the study includes interviews with the healthcare professionals and the members of the community. These interviews seek to capture detailed information on the community trends of tuberculosis transmission, health seeking practices and treatment. This part of the study assists in providing explanations and elaboration of the quantitative results especially concerning the interactions that the community has with Tuberculosis. Through the use of both qualitative and quantitative data, the study provides a better perspective on transmission of TB, as well as effectiveness and efficiency of public health interventions.

B. Methods of Analysis

This research uses quantitative and qualitative data to increase the comprehensiveness of the research for understanding TB transmission in Daet, Camarines Norte. Measuring quantitatively using Agent Based Simulation (ABS) and geographic information system (GIS) the flow of disease transmission across the barangays to determine rates of infection, high risk areas for transmission, and efficacy of control measures over time. Quantitative and Spatial descriptive tools will measure disease spread and locate regions that would need intervention. In this study, data collected through interviews with the healthcare professionals and community members will be analyzed based on the codes, themes, and patterns that are relevant to community health-seeking behavior and TB treatment compliance as well as beliefs and perceptions about TB. The qualitative data collected for the present study shall supplement the numerate analysis and provide essential information on behavioral indicators contributing to TB transmission.

C. Data Gathering

Data collection was done through purposively conducted interviews conducted in October with selected participants from the RHUI in Daet, Camarines Norte; health care providers and community members involved in TB diagnosis and treatment or TB cases personally experienced individuals. This method addressed qualitative characteristics of the community, their practices, perceived tuberculosis and other related factors that gave a fertile ground on which findings from Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) analyses could be based.

2020 - 2024 TB CASES					
NAME OF BARANGAY	0-4	5-24	25-54	55-above	
ALAWIHAAO	-	41	99	39	179
BARANGAY II	-	-	-	-	-
BIBIRAO	-	7	27	7	41
CALASGASAN	-	9	29	18	56
CAMAMBUGAN	1	30	45	34	110
DOGONGAN	-	12	36	8	56
MAGANG	1	22	47	19	89
MANCRUZ	1	9	16	10	36
PAMORANGON	-	13	20	14	47
SAN ISIDRO	-	-	1	-	1
BARANGAY I (POB.)	-	-	1	-	1
BARANGAY II (POB.)	-	8	9	15	32
BARANGAY IV (POB.)	-	-	-	1	1
TOTAL	3	151	330	165	649

The summarized data in Table 1 (as shown in Figure 1) provides the total number of TB cases from 2020 to 2024 across various barangays in Daet, Camarines Norte. The distribution of TB cases also follows the age grouping of 0–4, 5–24, 25–54, and 55 and above, with a total of 86 cases in the barangay in 2020, 102 cases in 2021, and 149 cases in 2022. Further, 166 cases in the barangay in 2023 and 146 cases in 2024. Some of these Barangays of concern include Alawihao with a higher case count followed by Magang. This age- and location-specific data is very important for spatial analysis of TB distribution and will be used for simulation and mapping parts of this research.

Outcome/Status	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	No Data	TOTAL
DIAGNOSED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ON TREATMENT	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
TREATMENT COMPLETED	24	20	1	-	-	-	45
CURED	19	10	-	-	-	-	29
LOST TO FF-UP	8	3	-	-	-	-	11
FAILED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NOT EVALUATED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DIED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	52	33	1	-	-	-	86

Figure 2. Patient Outcome/Status for 2020

Outcome/Status	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	No Data	TOTAL
DIAGNOSED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ON TREATMENT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TREATMENT COMPLETED	-	29	23	-	-	-	52
CURED	-	11	21	-	-	-	32
LOST TO FF-UP	-	15	1	-	-	-	16
FAILED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NOT EVALUATED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DIED	-	1	1	-	-	-	2
TOTAL	-	56	46	-	-	-	102

Figure 3. Patient Outcome/Status for 2021

Outcome/Status	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	No Data	TOTAL
DIAGNOSED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ON TREATMENT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TREATMENT COMPLETED	-	1	11	28	-	-	40
CURED	-	-	36	59	-	-	95
LOST TO FF-UP	-	-	9	3	-	-	12
FAILED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NOT EVALUATED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DIED	-	-	-	2	-	-	2
TOTAL	-	1	56	92	-	-	149

Figure 4. Patient Outcome/Status for 2022

Outcome/Status	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	No Data	TOTAL
DIAGNOSED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ON TREATMENT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TREATMENT COMPLETED	-	-	-	31	22	-	53
CURED	-	-	-	50	46	-	96
LOST TO FF-UP	-	-	-	6	3	-	9
FAILED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NOT EVALUATED	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
DIED	-	-	-	7	-	-	7
TOTAL	-	-	-	95	71	-	166

Figure 5. Patient Outcome/Status for 2023

Outcome/Status	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	No Data	TOTAL
DIAGNOSED	-	-	-	-	4	-	4
ON TREATMENT	-	-	-	-	-	88	88
TREATMENT COMPLETED	-	-	-	-	4	-	4
CURED	-	-	-	-	40	-	40
LOST TO FF-UP	-	-	-	-	4	-	4
FAILED	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
NOT EVALUATED	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DIED	-	-	-	-	6	-	6
TOTAL	-	-	-	-	59	88	147

Figure 6. Patient Outcome/Status for 2024

The five (5) tables in Figure 2 to 6 present a comprehensive comparison of patient outcomes over multiple years, showcasing variations in patient totals and treatment success. The first (1st) table in Figure 6 records the highest total at 86 cases, with 45 treatments completed and 29 patients cured. The second (2nd) table in Figure 7 shows a total of 102 cases, with 52 treatments completed and lower cure count of 32. The third (3rd) table in Figure 8 has 149 cases, indicating a substantial 40 treatments completed and 95 patients cured, while the fourth (4th) table in Figure 9 includes 166 cases with 53 treatments completed and the highest cure rate of 96. Lastly, the fifth (5th) table reports 147 cases, with 4 treatments completed and 40 cured.

PSA DAET MUNICIPALITY BARANGAYS POPULATION DATA	
ALAWIHAO	11,782
BARANGAY I	2,348
BARANGAY II	3,040
BARANGAY IV	8,133
BIBIRAO	2,173
CALASGASAN	4,141
CAMAMBUGAN	9,496
DOGONGAN	4,224
MAGANG	7,676
MANCRUZ (MANGCRUZ)	3,634
PAMORANGON	3,436
SAN ISIDRO	3,479

Figure 7. PSA Daet Municipality Barangays Population

The table above in figure 11 presents population data for the barangays of Daet Municipality, as reported by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) as of 2020. It includes population figures for various barangays, such as Alawihao (11,782 residents), Barangay IV (8,133 residents), and Camambugan (9,496 residents). The data highlights population distribution across the municipality, offering insight into the relative sizes of its barangays which can be used to create the Agent-based Simulation (ABS) and mapping model.

D. Initial Model Simulation

- Agent-based Simulation Model using Netlogo

Figure 8. Simulation Interface

Figure 12 is a simulation model created using NetLogo that describes the transmission of TB in the Daet Community, Camarines Norte. Parameters such as infection chance, infection radius, infection duration, mortality rate, recovery rate, and follow-up failure rate are used in the model, in order to model the spread of TB. These parameters can be adjusted on the sliders on the left to help perform a comparison of different values. The infection plot in the center represents actual counts of infected people, recovery, and deaths as a function of simulation ticks. On the right the spatial map demonstrates the flow of TB transmission within selected barangays wherein the triangular figures stand for people and icons depict barangays. This configuration provides an opportunity to perform an interactive assessment of infection dynamics, which will help to determine potential intervention measures.

Figure 8.1 Simulation of Model

It shows the real-time of the simulation and the ABS model for TB transmission within Daet, Camarines Norte. The infection plot on the left mirrors the cumulative time course of the infection where the line distinguishes infected (in red), recovered (in green), and deceased (in gray). These metrics work during the simulation process as they show how an infection rate grows, reaches its peak, and decreases.

The right panel is illustrated by colored triangles representing people that can only move within the framework of the barangays. The red stands for infected people, green for those who recovered and gray for those who died. Through considering these dynamic patterns, this model makes it possible to perform online monitoring of TB spread with the introduction of recovery rates and spots of transmission clusters. This visually acquired information helps in the identification of infection patterns existing in the various barangays, an essential input to the formulation of specific health promoting strategies.

• **QGIS Mapping Model**

Figure 9. QGIS map of TB case density of Daet barangays

This figure, the QGIS map shows one part of Daet, Camarines Norte, focusing on important landmarks and the rate of TB cases in different barangays. In the layers panel on the left the imported data sources from OpenStreetMap and particular shapefiles from barangay

are indicated. The map layers also contain the heat map layer work for TB cases showing density of workload for each barangay in different shades. Dark colors meaning higher levels of TB case prevalence which makes it easier to obtain information on regions with highly rated transmission rates.

The analysis is therefore achieved through the application of QGIS, which identifies areas of high disease transmission and promotes visualization of case incidences relative to important facilities such as hospitals, schools, and other important structures. With such a mapping, state and other health departments as well as researchers can know the risky areas or regions that require intervention based on geographical distribution of TB spread.

Formula Used:

$$\text{Rate per 1000} = \left(\frac{\text{Total Cases}}{\text{Population Size}} \right) \times 1000$$

1. This division gives the proportion of the population affected by the cases.

$$\left(\frac{\text{Total Cases}}{\text{Population Size}} \right)$$

For example, if there are 50 cases in a population of 10,000, the proportion is

$$\frac{50}{10000} = 0.005 \cdot 1000$$

2. The multiplier of 1,000 scales the proportion to a standard unit: "per 1,000 people."

Without this scaling, the value would remain as a fraction, which is less intuitive for comparison.

- Rate per 1000 is used to standardize the measure to allow easy comparison between areas with different population sizes.

Example: A barangay with 500 people and 5 cases might seem small compared to a barangay with 5,000 people and 50 cases, but their rates per 1,000 (10) are the same.

It simplifies understanding of the data for decision-makers and public health professionals. A rate of X per 1,000 is more actionable than a raw proportion.

Practical Example:

Barangay Alawihao 11,782 population, 48 cases.

$$\text{Rate per 1000} = (48/11,782) \cdot 1000 = 4.074 \text{ cases per 1000 people.}$$

This formula is a standard epidemiological method for analyzing and comparing disease prevalence across populations.

E. Initial Analyzation

These statistics in this project jointly depict the descriptive statistics, temporal and spatial trend of TB incidence in Daet, Camarines Norte. The figures 1 to 5 is a tribal map with TB cases per age group, which characterizes regions and age ranges with the highest infection rates across the barangay for the year 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024. While figure 12 and figure 12.1 illustrate a model of TB using NetLogo where various attributes may be tuned to make the examination of disease spread and of the recovery rate over time. The simulation interface and especially the visual result assists with the explanation why and how certain factors affect the transmission of disease. Lastly the figure 13 is a QGIS map of TB case density of Daet barangays that makes it easy to identify hotspots and spatial patterns. Altogether these figures are useful to assess transmission dynamics of TB taking into account age, geographical distribution and simulation based modeling for targeted interventions.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. QGIS Mapping Model

Figure 10. TB Outbreaks per Barangay by Age Group in 2020

Based on the map, Barangay Bibirao recorded the highest TB incidence, with a rate of 4.142 cases per 1,000 population. In contrast, Calasgasan reported a lower incidence rate of 1.932 cases per 1,000 population.

Barangay	Age_0_4	Age_5_24	Age_25_54	Age_55	Total_case	Population	IncidentR
1 Bibirao	0	1	6	2	9	2173	4.142
2 Calasgasan	0	2	3	3	8	4141	1.932
3 Camabugan	0	4	11	3	18	9496	1.896
4 Alawihao	0	2	14	6	22	11782	1.867
5 Pamorangan	0	1	2	2	5	3436	1.455
6 Magang	0	3	6	2	11	7676	1.433
7 Dogongan	0	2	3	1	6	4224	1.420
8 Mancruz	0	3	1	1	5	3634	1.376
9 San Isidro	0	0	0	0	0	3479	0
10 Barangay II	0	0	0	0	0	3040	0
11 Barangay I	0	0	0	0	0	2348	0
12 Barangay IV	0	0	0	0	0	8133	0

Figure. 10.1 TB Outbreaks Rankings per Barangay by Age Group in 2020

Figure 10.2 TB Outbreaks per Barangay by Age Group in 2021

Based on the map, Barangay Pamorangan (3.783) and Barangay II (3.618) recorded the highest TB incidence rates. In contrast, Barangay Dogongan (1.657), Barangay Magang (1.172), and Barangay Mancruz (1.651) had very low TB incidence rates.

Barangay	Age_0_4	Age_5_24	Age_25_54	Age_55	Total_case	Population	IncidentR
1	0	5	5	3	13	3436	3.783
2 Barangay II	0	2	3	6	11	3040	3.618
3 Bibirao	0	1	4	1	6	2173	2.761
4 Alawihao	0	10	15	4	29	11782	2.461
5 Calasgasan	0	2	5	3	10	4141	2.415
6 Camabugan	0	6	7	7	20	9496	2.106
7 Dogongan	0	0	2	5	7	4224	1.657
8 Mancruz	0	0	3	3	6	3634	1.651
9 Magang	0	4	5	0	9	7676	1.172
10 San Isidro	0	0	0	0	0	3479	0
11 Barangay I	0	0	0	0	0	2348	0
12 Barangay IV	0	0	0	0	0	8133	0

Figure. 10.3 TB Outbreaks Rankings per Barangay by Age Group in 2021

Figure 10.4 TB Outbreaks per Barangay by Age Group in 2022

Based on the data, Barangay Dogongan (4.261), Pamorangan (3.783), and Calasgasan (3.864) had very high TB incidence rates, indicating areas of critical concern. In contrast, Barangay Magang (1.694) recorded very low TB incidence rates.

Barangay	Age_0_4	Age_5_24	Age_25_54	Age_55	Total_case	Population	IncidentR
1 Dogongan	0	4	10	4	18	4224	4.261
2 Calasgasan	0	2	7	7	16	4141	3.864
3 Pamorangan	0	5	5	3	13	3436	3.783
4 Mancruz	0	0	5	2	13	3634	3.577
5 Alawihao	0	9	21	10	40	11782	3.395
6 Bibirao	0	1	4	2	7	2173	3.221
7 Camabugan	0	6	12	9	27	9496	2.843
8 Barangay II	0	3	0	5	8	3040	2.632
9 Magang	0	3	8	2	13	7676	1.694
10 San Isidro	0	0	0	0	0	3479	0
11 Barangay I	0	0	0	0	0	2348	0
12 Barangay IV	0	0	0	0	0	8133	0

Figure. 10.5 TB Outbreaks Rankings per Barangay by Age Group in 2022

Figure 10.6 TB Outbreaks per Barangay by Age Group in 2023

Based on the map, Barangay Magang (4.169), Pamorangan (4.075), and Alawihao (4.074) recorded very high TB incidence rates, indicating areas of significant concern. Barangay II, with an incidence rate of 1.974, was categorized as having very low TB cases.

Barangay	Age_0_4	Age_5_24	Age_25_54	Age_55	Total_case	Population	IncidentR
1 Magang	0	7	16	9	32	7676	4.169
2 Pamorangan	0	7	7	3	14	3436	4.075
3 Alawihao	0	10	25	13	48	11782	4.074
4 Bibirao	0	1	5	8	8	2173	3.682
5 Dogongan	0	4	9	0	13	4224	3.078
6 Calasgasan	0	2	8	2	12	4141	2.898
7 Mancruz	1	2	5	2	10	3634	2.752
8 Camabugan	1	9	4	9	23	9496	2.422
9 Barangay II	0	1	3	2	6	3040	1.974
10 San Isidro	0	0	0	0	0	3479	0
11 Barangay I	0	0	0	0	0	2348	0
12 Barangay IV	0	0	0	0	0	8133	0

Figure. 10.7 TB Outbreaks Rankings per Barangay by Age Group in 2023

Figure 10.8 TB Outbreaks per Barangay by Age Group in 2024

In 2024, Barangay Bibirao recorded a very high TB incidence rate of 5.062, highlighting it as a critical area for intervention. Barangay IV (0.123), Barangay I (1.645), and San Isidro (0.287) were classified as having very low TB incidence rates.

Barangay	Age_0_4	Age_5_24	Age_25_54	Age_55	Total_case	Population	IncidentR
1 Bibirao	0	0	3	8	11	2173	5.062
2 Alawihao	0	10	24	6	40	11782	3.395
3 Magang	1	5	12	6	24	7676	3.127
4 Dogongan	0	2	9	1	12	4224	2.841
5 Mancruz	0	3	2	5	10	3634	2.752
6 Pamorangan	0	0	3	6	9	3436	2.619
7 Calasgasan	0	1	6	3	10	4141	2.415
8 Camabugan	0	5	11	6	22	9496	2.317
9 Barangay II	0	2	2	1	5	3040	1.645
10 Barangay I	0	0	1	0	1	2348	0.426
11 San Isidro	0	0	0	1	1	3479	0.287
12 Barangay IV	0	0	0	1	1	8133	0.123

Figure. 10.9 TB Outbreaks Rankings per Barangay by Age Group in 2024

GIS Map Summary:

Figure 10 illustrates the TB outbreaks per barangay in 2020 - 2024, categorized by age groups. On the map, blue represents areas with a very high incidence of TB cases, while red indicates areas with a very low incidence. The orange indicates low incidents, yellow for medium and green for high incidents. From 2020 to 2024, the TB incidence rates across barangays showed significant variations.

In 2020, Barangay Bibirao recorded the highest TB incidence rate at 4.142 cases per 1,000 population, while Barangay Mancruz had the lowest rate at 1.376.

By 2021, Barangay Pamorangan emerged as the area with the highest TB rate at 3.783 cases per 1,000 population, and Barangay Magang had the lowest rate at 1.172.

In 2022, Barangay Dogongan experienced the highest TB rate, with 4.261 cases per 1,000 population, while Barangay Magang reported the lowest rate at 1.694. The trend shifted in 2023, with Barangay Magang recording the highest incident rate of 4.169 cases per 1,000 population, and Barangay II reporting the lowest rate at 1.974.

By 2024, Barangay Bibirao again recorded the highest TB incidence rate, reaching 5.062 cases per 1,000 population, while Barangay IV had the lowest rate at 0.123. This data highlights the fluctuations in TB incidence across the years and emphasizes the need for targeted interventions in high-risk barangays.

B. Agent Based Simulation Model

Figure 11. TB Outbreaks Without Intervention per Barangay by Age Group (2020-2024)

The first simulation presents the situation that develops if TB infection increases without control measures from 2020 to 2024. Tuberculosis cases accumulate rapidly and gradually over time. Some age groups, like children and working adults, are affected more because they interact with more people. The visualization example displays many red turtles – agents that move around – that symbolize infected individuals and are packed more tightly as the disease advances. Some barangays are hit harder than others, especially in places with more people or more social activities. Without intervention, TB spreads rapidly, leading to a serious health problem that is difficult to control.

Figure 11.1 TB Outbreaks With Intervention per Barangay by Age Group (2020-2024)

The second simulation shows what happens when interventions like treatment, health education, and vaccination are used to fight TB. These results indicate that TB cases rise in the beginning, then decrease gradually and the rate at which they are decreasing becomes steeper as time goes on. Unlike the first simulation that had more red turtles meaning that more people are infected, the visual simulation reveals that few red turtles hence few people are infected. Although some barangays still have cases, the rate of infections, unlike

others, is slower and there are some regions where the number of new cases reduces with time. This shows that interventions can effectively reduce the number of TB infections and control the spread of the disease.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study shows how the combination of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) can be used to then assess and forecast TB transmission patterns in Daet, Camarines Norte. The findings indicate that geographical distribution and time trend of TB cases varies and certain BHs /Barangays such as Alawihao and Biraao are identified as TB prevalence areas. Mobility rates, infection probabilities, and healthcare service accessibility became crucial key predictors of transmission.

The integrated analysis of the work based on the use of the ABS and GIS helped to identify potential effectiveness of the intervention measures and demonstrate the necessity of developing individual programs for the targeted improvement of people’s health and increasing the effectiveness of the recovery stages. Simulation models were useful for operational monitoring as well as for planning, and GIS applications helped to focus on the most critical areas to address.

Therefore, using GIS, and ABS in the current study demonstrates their efficiency in enhancing TB control and prevention. In this way, policy makers and the authorities on public health can effectively apply these tools in order to implement data analysis techniques to fight the transmission of TB and optimize the allocation of resources. The next studies could potentially expand the introduction of other parameters, including climate and economical conditions, for improving disease modeling and intervention approaches.

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